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Impact Factor: 0.98

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN MARKET ORIENTATION, INTERNATIONAL ORIENTATION, AND EXPORT MARKET SUCCESS: AN EMPIRICAL RESEARCH ON SMES IN TEHRAN

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ABSTRACT

The present study attempts to investigate the relationship between international orientation and market orientation from two aspects i.e. customer orientation and competitor orientation and also the contribution of these factors to export success of small and medium sized manufacturing companies is scrutinized. Research hypotheses were tested by analyzing data gathered through questionnaire which was distributed among 210 managers of small and medium manufacturing companies. Convenience sampling in Tehran was applied for pinpointing companies and structural equation modeling was conducted for data analysis. Results are indicative of a positive and significant relationship between market orientation and international orientation, between market orientation and export market success, and also between international orientation and export market success. Therefore, it can be concluded that those firms of more international and market orientation, were better at export.

Keywords: Strategic orientation, Market orientation, International orientation, Export market success, Small and medium-sized enterprises

INTRODUCTION :

Nowadays, export has increasingly gained importance so that abundant companies all around the world are making an attempt to cover markets beyond their national borders by supplying goods and services (Keegan, 2013). Export plays a pivotal role in doing business with other countries and their companies and enables higher profitability, reforms resource exploiting, generates jobs and improves commercial balance (Barker and Kaynak, 2015).

Usually, huge expenses are allocated by governments to export promotion programs of small and medium size companies since export rate of these companies contributes greatly to the national economy of each country. Export promotion programs of governments enhance the export rate of small and medium companies more than that of large export corporations. Needless to say, export conduct of small and medium companies and factors leading to their export success are of significant importance and defining these kinds of factors can act as valuable guidelines for administrators and policy makers based on which they can devise and execute their export policies (Katsikeas et al., 1996).

As a natural consequence, factors impacting upon export performance of companies have drawn wide attention of researchers. Empirical researches in this regard could have identify a wide range of such factors (e. g. Zou and Stan, 1998, Ellis, 2006, Murray et al., 2007, Cadogan et al., 2009). Zou and Stan (1998), studied the factors affecting export performance and categorized them into two groups; internal factors and external ones. They per se consist of controllable and non –controllable factors. Internal controllable factors include export marketing strategies and management attitudes and perceptions. Internal uncontrollable factors include management characteristics, firm's characteristics and competencies. External controllable factors include industry characteristics and foreign and domestic market characteristics. Each above mentioned factor was divided into

other sub-factors and ultimately thirty three independent variables were analyzed. The present research is focused upon small and medium exporters and among internal controllable factors affecting upon export, it studies strategic orientation, international orientation, and market orientation as potential qualifications required for successful export performance.

Most of researches studying export performance have focused on managers' international inclinations and demonstrate that strategic orientation impresses export success positively (Leonidou and Katsikeas, 1996, Aspelund et al., 2007, Knight and Kim, 2009). However, despite many findings implying a positive relationship between market orientation and companies' performance (e. g. Kirca et al., 2005, Ellis, 2006, Ellis, 2007, Grinstein, 2008), those researches which have considered firm's strategic orientations as the unit of analysis, have challenged this consistent positive relationship (Eibe Sørensen and Koed Madsen, 2012). These suspicions are mainly derived from empirical studies which have included environmental moderators within the relationship between market orientation and performance (Cadogan et al., 2002, Rose and Shoham, 2002, Cadogan et al., 2003) and represent non-linear relationships.

Murray et al. (2007), state probably important variables such as firm's degree of internationalization and its foreign activities may have probably not been considered in models of relationship between market orientation and export market success. This study also demonstrates that exporting firms active in various foreign markets are more challenged in adopting effective market orientation. Ellis (2007) as well, emphasizes on diversity of foreign markets as a potential determining factor impacting on the relationship between market orientation and performance of firms. This attitude is somehow against common internationalization literature in which increasing market commitments and experiential learning are stressed as better international performance drives (e. g. Johanson and Vahlne, 2009). In other words, more widespread studies are required for clarifying this critical issue (Eibe Sørensen and Koed Madsen, 2012). Therefore, the present study scrutinizes the relationship between strategic orientations – international and market orientations- and export market success more precisely. Thereby, both orientations are investigated since they may complement one another and signal an effective and positive correlation.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework of present research is based on resource-based view toward firms (Wernerfelt, 1984, Barney, 1991). Advocates of this attitude believe that better performance based on resources and competencies is so valuable and strategies designed based on resources are not easily imitated and policies and trends are designed for exploiting aforementioned capabilities and resources. According to this viewpoint, firms' strategic orientation is representative of their strategic capabilities and directs them to superior performance (Hult et al., 2005). For instance, market orientation is a strategic capability, imitation of which costs competitors hugely (Slater and Narver, 1998, Day, 2011). Strategic orientation implies a series of wide strategic options which guarantees permanent superior performance and enables employees and managers to reach superior performance (Gatignon and Xuereb, 1997). Present study deals with two strategic orientations which potentially have the capability of creating superior performance for firm in beyond border activities. They are international orientation and market orientation.

International orientation refers to senior management attitudes and resource allocation to international activities (Eibe Sørensen and Koed Madsen, 2012). Firms with a strong international orientation tend to possess distinctive competencies and outlook. They tend to be characterized by managerial vision and proactive organizational culture for developing particular resources aimed at achieving company goals in foreign markets (Knight and Kim, 2009). In fact, international inclination is a mental issue so that managers conceive the whole world as their market and try their best in doing business with international partners and customers. It is however of vital importance those senior managers has clear commitment of resources and expand organizational culture to motivate their employees to participate in international activities (Eibe Sørensen and Koed Madsen, 2012).

Market orientation is a commitment to understanding latent and expressed needs of customers and capabilities and programs of competitors through gaining information by a systematic and predicted method. Sharing this information in the organization through concentrated and coordinated activities creates superior value for customers (Slater and Narver, 1995). Actually, market orientation is one of the aspects of organizational culture which prioritizes customers and endows them with high value and it is realized via a wide range of organizational behavior and activities carried out for gaining and disseminating customer and competitors' related information and timely response based on this information (Kohli and Jaworski, 1990, Narver and Slater, 1990). Some researchers have approved the positive relationship between market orientation, operational and financial performance (Hult et al., 2005, Kirca et al., 2005, Ellis, 2006). As well, Eibe Sørensen and Koed Madsen (2012) have ratified the relationship between market orientation and export market success. Therefore, the first research hypothesis is as follows;

H1: there is positive relationship between market orientation, and export market success.

Narver and Slater (1990) have defined market orientation by three main components; customer orientation, competitor orientation, and inter-functional coordination. Customer orientation and competitor orientation include all activities done for earning information about customers and competitors in the aimed market and dissemination of this information throughout the organization. The third component i.e. inter-functional coordination takes place based on customer and competitor information and organization's coordinated measures for creating superior value for purchasers. It is generally beyond marketing unit. In line with Narver and Slater (1990), the present study has scrutinized two symmetrical components; market orientation- the customer orientation and market orientation-the competitor orientation component (Sørensen and Slater, 2008, Eibe Sørensen and Koed Madsen, 2012). Thus, hypothesis 1 can be split into two following hypotheses;

H1a: there is positive relationship between market orientation-customer orientation and export market success.

H1b: there is positive relationship between market orientation-competitor orientation and export market success.

On the other hand, high international orientation necessitates thorough knowledge about international markets, and the capability of responding and deciding based on this vast knowledge (Eibe Sørensen and Koed Madsen, 2012). A research carried out about knowledge based firms proved that those firms of vast organizational capabilities in gathering and sharing information will have better international performance (Kuivalainen et al., 2004). Meanwhile, market orientation is a prerequisite for developing and extracting such informative capabilities and properties based on market (Slater et al., 2012). Therefore, second research hypothesis is defined as follows;

H2: there is positive relationship between market orientation and international orientation.

Consequently, regarding the two mentioned components of market orientation (Sørensen and Slater, 2008), the second hypothesis can be split as follows;

H2a: there is positive relationship between market orientation-customer orientation and international orientation.

H2b: there is positive relationship between market orientation- competitor orientation and international orientation.

Knight and Kim (2009) argue there is positive relationship between international orientation and export performance. They assert that management's intellectual mode must be reflective of their companies' international strategies. It requires managers to encourage their employees to seek opportunities in foreign markets and emphasize that organizational activity and adaptability for successful competition in foreign markets is vital. On the other hand, Eibe Sørensen and Koed Madsen (2012) have also stresses the existence of a positive relationship between international inclination and export market success. Therefore, the third research hypothesis can be stated as follows;

H3: there is positive relationship between firm's international orientation and its successful export success.

The conceptual model of present research will be as depicted in figure 1.

Figure1. The Research Conceptual Model

Research Methodology

The model of present research was defined based on data gathered from 210 questionnaires distributed by convenience sampling through managers' of small to medium sized firms in Tehran and it was tested relying on structural equation modeling and by means of LISREL software. In fact, data gathering was conducted by referring to librarian documents and distributing questionnaires.

The questionnaire was made up of three main parts; 1- preamble; in which the objective of data gathering by questionnaire and the necessity of respondents' cooperation for supplying required data were declared. To this end, preciousness of gathered data was emphasized so as to have participants respond appropriately to questions; 2- demographic questions; As shown in the table1, this section was consisted of 6 questions regarding level of education, age, gender, organizational status, the number of staff, and export activities background; 3- items related to research variables; This section entails 30 questions. 8 items measure "market orientation-customer orientation", 10 items measure "market orientation-competitor orientation" (Sørensen and Slater, 2008, Eibe Sørensen and Koed Madsen, 2012), 8 items measured "international inclination" (Eibe Sørensen and Koed Madsen, 2012, Knight and Cavusgil, 2004, Knight and Kim, 2009), and 4 items measured "export performance" (Hult et al., 2005). Likert five-point scale was applied for designing the later section.

Table1. Demographic Characteristics of Respondents (n=210)

variable		Frequency	%	mode
Gender	male	180	85.71%	male
	female	30	14.29%	
Age	18-24	24	11.43%	25-34
	25-34	85	40.48%	
	35-44	62	29.52%	
	45-54	30	14.29%	
	Over 55	9	4.29%	
Level of Education	Below Diploma	8	3.81%	BA
	Diploma	68	32.38%	
	BA	93	44.29%	
	MA	35	16.67%	
	PhD	6	2.86%	
Number of Staff	Below 50	125	59.52%	Below 50
	50-100	43	20.48%	
	100-150	11	5.24%	
	150-200	17	8.10%	
	Over 200	14	6.67%	
Export Activities Experience (year)	One year or less	8	3.81%	Over 7
	1-3	22	10.48%	
	3-5	28	13.33%	
	5-7	33	15.71%	
	Over 7	119	56.67%	
Organizational Status	Managing Director	67	31.90%	Managing Director
	Senior Manager	45	21.43%	
	Middle Manager	48	22.86%	
	Senior Expert	18	8.57%	
	Expert	32	15.24%	

Results

In order to test the relationship between research variables, structural equation modeling was applied (Joreskog et al., 1979, Bagozzi and Yi, 2012). Figure 2, shows the model in standardized estimation situation and figure 3 shows the research model in t-value situation which is indicative of the relationship between observed variables (rectangle, which is somehow directly measured by the researcher) and latent variables (circle, which is inferred from relationships or correlations between measured variables).

In structural equation modeling, coefficients are divided into two groups. The first group implies the relationship between latent variables (circle) and observed variables (rectangle). These equations are called loading factors. The second group shows the relationship between latent and latent variables and are used to test hypotheses. They are called path coefficients. Regarding the model for estimating coefficients, loading factor and path coefficients can be estimated. According to this model, path coefficient is significant at 95% level, if t value is not included within -1.96 to +1.96. If t value is within this interval, path coefficient will not be significant. Path coefficient is significant at 99% level if t value is out of -2.58 to +2.58.

Note.MO-CUS = Market Orientation-Customer Orientation, MO-COM = Market Orientation-Competitor Orientation, INTO = International Orientation, EMS = Export Market Success

Figure2. The research model in standardized estimation situation

Note.MO-CUS = Market Orientation-Customer Orientation, MO-COM = Market Orientation-Competitor Orientation, INTO = International Orientation, EMS = Export Market Success

Figure3. The research model in t-value situation

To analyze construct validity, confirmative factor analysis was used. The results of confirmative factor analysis of research constructs are summarized in table 2. As shown in the table, t-values indicate that all loadings are significant at 0.001. It can be asserted that the research enjoys good construct validity. In addition, all Cronbach's alpha values are larger than 0.7, indicating a good reliability(Cramer, 1994).

Table2. Loading Factors of Research Constructs

Factor Item	MO-CUS	MO-COM	INTO	EMS	Cronbach's alpha
MOCUS1	0.54**				0.807
MOCUS2	0.56**				
MOCUS3	0.44**				
MOCUS4	0.57**				
MOCUS5	0.68**				
MOCUS6	0.57**				
MOCUS7	0.53**				
MOCUS8	0.94**				
MOCOM1		0.76**			0.900
MOCOM2		0.69**			
MOCOM3		0.73**			
MOCOM4		0.56**			
MOCOM5		0.76**			
MOCOM6		0.71**			
MOCOM7		0.76**			
MOCOM8		0.61**			
MOCOM9		0.63**			
MOCOM10		0.68**			
INTO1			0.49**		0.826
INTO2			0.52**		
INTO3			0.60**		
INTO4			0.55**		
INTO5			0.67**		
INTO6			0.57**		
INTO7			0.97**		
INTO8			0.77**		
EMS1				0.65**	0.845
EMS2				0.69**	
EMS3				0.85**	
EMS4				0.86**	
Notes: **p < 0.01					

Generally, in structural equation modeling, model's goodness of fit is not interpreted merely based on individual indexes. In fact, all indexes must be interpreted together. Table 3 shows recommended (Hair, 2010), and actual values of some fit indexes. As shown in the table, the various indexes used show that the fit of the saturated model is good.

Table3. The model's goodness of fit indices

indexes	chi ² /df	GFI	AGFI	CFI	NFI	NNFI	RMSEA
Recommended value	< 3	> 0.90	> 0.80	> 0.90	> 0.90	> 0.90	< 0.08
Actual value	2.10	0.90	0.83	0.95	0.91	0.95	0.073
Notes: chi ² /df is the ratio between Chi-square and degrees of freedom, GFI is Goodness of Fit Index, AGFI is the Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index, CFI is the Comparative Fit Index, NFI is the Normed Fit Index, NNFI is the Non-Normed Fit Index, RMSEA is Root Mean Square Error of Approximation							

Considering the results of path coefficient and t value reflected in figure 2, 3, and table 4, there is positive and significant relationship between market orientation-customer orientation and international orientation($\gamma=0.32$, $t=4.20$), between market orientation-competitor orientation and international orientation ($\gamma=0.45$, $t=5.17$), between market orientation-customer orientation and export market success ($\gamma=0.19$, $t=2.87$)and also between international orientation and export market success($\beta=0.54$, $t=4.93$) at 99% significance level. It was also found that there is positive and significant relationship between market orientation-competitor orientation and export market success ($\gamma=0.14$, $t=1.99$) at 95% significance level.

Table 4. Summary of Hypotheses Tests

Research hypothesis	Hypothesis	Path coefficient	t-value	Significance	The result of research hypothesis
H1a	MO-CUS →EMS	0.19	2.87	$p < 0.01$	supported
H1b	MO-COM →EMS	0.14	1.99	$p < 0.05$	supported
H2a	MO-CUS →INTO	0.32	4.20	$p < 0.01$	supported
H2b	MO-COM →INTO	0.45	5.17	$p < 0.01$	supported
H3	INTO →EMS	0.54	4.93	$p < 0.01$	supported

Notes:
MO-CUS =Market Orientation-Customer Orientation, MO-COM =Market Orientation- Competitor Orientation, INTO = International Orientation, EMS = Export Market Success

Discussion

All three research hypotheses were supported based on data gathered from 210 managers of small and medium manufacturing firms of Tehran and statistical outcomes of structural equation modeling. It was found out that there is significant relationship between market orientation- customer orientation and export market success at 99% significance level ($\gamma=0.19$, $t=2.87$). Since γ is positive, it can be stated that the relationship between two variables is both positive and parallel. Therefore, the more market orientation-customer orientation increases in the positive direction, the more export performance success will also increase in the same direction and vice versa. As well, there is significant relationship between market orientation-competitor orientation and export market success at 95% significance level ($\gamma=0.14$, $t=1.99$). Thus, since γ is positive, it can be claimed that at 99% significance level, the relationship between two variables is both positive and parallel. In addition, It was found out that there is significant relationship between market orientation- customer orientation and international orientation ($\gamma=0.32$, $t=4.20$), as well as between market orientation-competitor orientation and international orientation ($\gamma=0.45$, $t=5.17$). Hence, those firms of higher market orientation (at both aspects i.e. customer orientation and competitor orientation) will show more powerful international orientation, too.

As well, it was revealed that there is significant relationship at 99% significance level between international orientation and export market success ($\beta=0.54$, $t= 4.93$). As β is positive, the relationship between the two variables is both positive and parallel. As a natural consequence, the more international orientation enhances in the positive direction, the more export market success will boost.

Accordingly, it is suggested that small and medium firms reinforce international orientation and market orientation culture so as to improve their export performance. Nonetheless, since sampling was carried out only among small and medium firms of Tehran, it is recommended that the same research be implemented in other organizations and based on a larger sample. This will considerably enable generalization of research findings. On the other hand, since present research studied the direct relationship between market orientation and international orientation with export market success, further studies can study the impacts of moderators such as market portfolio diversity.

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Ali Abdolvand & Eshghipour / The Relationship between Market Orientation, International Orientation, and Export Market Success :An Empirical Research on SMEs in Tehran

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